

Lanthanide complexes of tetradentate macrocyclic ligand : Synthesis and spectroscopic investigation

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Abstract : In the present paper, the lanthanide complexes derived from (1,5,8,12-tetraaza-2,4,9,11-tetramethyl cyclotetraaza-1,4,8,11-tetraene) were synthesized. The general composition of the complexes is $[\text{Ln}(\text{L})\text{X}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{X}$, where $\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}$ and Eu and $\text{X} = \text{NO}_3^-$ and Cl^- . The ligand was characterized on the basis of elemental analyses, IR, Mass and ^1H NMR spectral studies. All the complexes were characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, IR, Mass, electronic spectral techniques and thermal studies. The ligand acts as a tetradentate chelate and coordinates through four nitrogen atoms of azomethine groups. The lanthanum complexes are diamagnetic while the other Ln^{III} complexes are paramagnetic due to the presence of $4f^n$ unpaired electrons. The spectral parameters i.e. nephelauxetic effect (β), covalency factor ($b^{1/2}$), Sinha parameter ($\delta\%$) and covalency angular overlap parameter (η) have been calculated from absorption spectra of Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} complexes. These parameters suggest the metal-ligand covalent bonding. In the present study, the complexes show the coordination number seven.

Keywords : Tetradentate macrocycle, metal complexes, lanthanide(III).

Introduction

The macrocyclic ligands have attracted a considerable interest in the field of coordination chemistry because of their capacity to bind and transport metal ions, surprising coordination environment, unexpected reactivity and their rich chemical behavior^{1,2}. Macrocyclic ligands form metal complexes, which in general are thermodynamically more stable and more selective metal ion chelates than open chain analogues (macrocyclic effect)^{3,4}. Their lanthanide complexes have been widely examined in the last two decades⁵⁻⁷ because of their potential applications in biology, medicine and material science^{8,9}. In spite of these facts, the organolanthanide macrocycles have been scarcely reported because of the reason that the coordination number of lanthanide metal ions is higher i.e. 8-12 than that of the transition metal ions i.e. 4-6 thus increasing the inscrutability of self assembled structure¹⁰.

In view of the above discussion and proceeding the research work about the rare earth chemistry, in this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Ln^{III} complexes of macrocyclic ligand derived from acetyl acetone and ethylene diamine.

Experimental

Materials :

Metal salts (E. Merck) were commercially available pure samples. Other chemicals (Fluka) and solvents were used as received.

Physical measurements :

The ^1H NMR spectrum of ligand was recorded at room temperature on a model Bruker Advance DPX-300 spectrometer operating at 300 MHz using CDCl_3 as solvent and tetramethyl silane as an internal standard. IR spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a FT-IR BX-II spectrometer in the region $200-4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Electron impact mass spectrum was recorded on JEOL JMS, DX-303 mass spectrometer. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UVmini-1240 spectrophotometer. Elemental analysis was carried out on a Carbo-Erba EA 1106 analyzer and the nitrogen content of complexes was determined using Kjeldahl's method. Molar conductivity was measured on an Elico (CM 82T) conductivity bridge using prepared solution of the complex in DMSO. Magnetic moment was determined at room temperature on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as a calibrant. The

Table I. Analytical data of the ligand and Ln^{III} complexes

Ligand/ Complexes	M.W. (Found)	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Elemental analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
							M	C	H	N
$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4$	248	Cream	244	70	-	-	67.74 (67.69)	9.67 (9.63)	22.58 (22.51)	
$[\text{La}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	511	Light brown	>300	68	Dia.	110	27.17 (27.11)	32.84 (32.80)	5.08 (5.02)	10.94 (10.89)
$[\text{La}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	591	Light brown	>300	62	Dia.	98	23.51 (23.47)	28.42 (28.38)	4.39 (4.32)	16.58 (16.52)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	516	Light purple	>300	65	2.26	93	27.87 (27.81)	32.52 (32.47)	5.03 (4.99)	10.84 (10.79)
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	596	Off white	>300	62	3.62	108	24.16 (24.12)	28.18 (28.15)	4.36 (4.29)	16.44 (16.42)
$[\text{Ce}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	592	Light brown	>300	68	3.61	104	23.64 (23.62)	28.37 (28.35)	4.39 (4.36)	16.55 (16.49)
$[\text{Sm}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	523	Creamy brown	>300	65	1.64	107	28.75 (28.72)	32.12 (32.09)	4.97 (4.91)	10.70 (10.68)
$[\text{Eu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	525	Yellow	>300	64	3.36	112	28.95 (28.87)	32.00 (31.94)	4.95 (4.89)	10.67 (10.59)

Fig. 1. IR bands due to (a and b) NO₃ anions and (c and d) ν (H₂O), ρ ν (H₂O) and M-N.

¹H NMR spectrum :

The ¹H NMR spectrum of the ligand L was recorded in CDCl₃ solution and was depicted in Fig. 2. The spectrum exhibits the three singlets; one at ca. δ 2.2999 ppm

(12H, s, 4CH₃^a), second at ca. δ 3.6375 ppm (4H, s, 2CH₂^b) and third at ca. δ 4.7514 ppm (8H, s, 4CH₂^c). These signals indicate the presence of three types of the different protons in the ligand²⁰.

Mass spectrum of the ligand :

The mass spectrum of the ligand is given in Fig. 3. In the mass spectrum, the characteristic groups of the peaks are found to be centered around mass numbers corresponding to the molecular ion M⁺, M⁺-15, M⁺-30, M⁺-45, M⁺-60 at *m/z* 248 (100%), 233, 218, 203, 188 (50%). The molecular ion peak is also the base peak. The later four groups of peaks are very specific and are as result of stepwise removal of methyl radicals from macrocyclic ring. The peak at *m/z* 188 is due to the macrocyclic moiety, which is completely free from methyl groups, and this peak indicates the formation of macrocyclic ring. Other peaks observed at 15, 26, 38 μ , 42, 66, 108 and 150 are due to the different fragmented ions²¹. The possible fragmentation path of the ligand is given in Scheme 2.

Mass spectrum of the complexes :

The fragment of the mass spectrum of [La(L)Cl₂·H₂O]Cl : 517 [(LaC₁₄H₂₆N₄OCl₃ + 6H)⁺, 42%], 482 [(LaC₁₄H₂₆N₄OCl₂ + 6H)⁺, 100%], 460 [(LaC₁₄H₂₄N₄Cl₂ + 2H)⁺, 48%], 389 [(LaC₁₄H₂₄N₄ + 2H)⁺, 61%], 362 [(LaC₁₂H₂₁N₄ + 2H)⁺, 40%], 323 [(LaC₉H₁₆N₄ + 4H)⁺, 30%], 184 [(C₉H₁₆N₄ + 4H)⁺, 34%], 139 [(La)³⁺, 68%], 128 [(C₇H₁₂N₂ + 4H)⁺, 52%], 74 [(C₃H₆N₂ + 4H)⁺, 26%] and 56 [(C₂H₄N₂)⁺, 58%].

The fragment of the mass spectrum of [La(L)(NO₃)₂·H₂O]NO₃ : 593 [(LaC₁₄H₂₆N₇O₁₀ + 2H)⁺, 55%], 531 [(LaC₁₄H₂₆N₆O₇ + 2H)⁺, 40%], 407 [(LaC₁₄H₂₆N₄O + 2H)⁺, 37%], 391 [(LaC₁₄H₂₄N₄ + 4H)⁺, 100%], 375 [(LaC₁₃H₂₂N₄ + 2H)⁺, 25%], 321 [(LaC₉H₁₆N₄ + 2H)⁺, 36%], 180 [(C₉H₁₆N₄)⁺, 48%], 139 [(La)³⁺, 70%], 68 [(C₅H₈)⁺, 30%], 54 [(C₄H₆)⁺, 20%] and 27 [(C₂H₃)⁺, 47%].

The fragment of the mass spectrum of [Nd(L)Cl₂·H₂O]Cl : 519 [(NdC₁₄H₂₆N₄OCl₃ + 3H)⁺, 45%], 484 [(NdC₁₄H₂₆N₄OCl₂ + 6H)⁺, 44%], 394 [(NdC₁₄H₂₄N₄Cl₂ + 2H)⁺, 100%], 378 [(NdC₁₃H₂₂N₄)⁺, 34%], 180 [(C₉H₁₆N₄)⁺, 42%], 144 [(Nd)³⁺, 70%], 124 [(C₇H₁₂N₂)⁺, 50%], 97 [(C₅H₉N₂)⁺, 62%] and 56 [(C₂H₄N₂)⁺, 54%].

Table 2. IR spectral data of the ligand and its Ln^{III} complexes (cm⁻¹)

Ligand/ Complexes	$\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$	$\nu\text{M}-\text{N}$	$\rho\text{r}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\rho\text{w}(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu\text{M}-\text{Cl}$
$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4$	1600	-	-	-	-
$[\text{La}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	1627	426	706	542	298
$[\text{La}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	1624	421	702	615	-
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	1625	441	733	562	312
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	1623	421	670	546	-
$[\text{Ce}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	1624	435	652	494	-
$[\text{Sm}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	1628	445	780	528	302
$[\text{Eu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	1632	430	671	592	308

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of ligand.

The fragment of the mass spectrum of $[\text{Nd}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$: 598 $[(\text{NdC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_7\text{O}_{10} + 2\text{H})^+$, 60%], 536 $[(\text{NdC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_7 + 2\text{H})^+$, 52%], 412 $[(\text{NdC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O} + 2\text{H})^+$, 100%], 367 $[(\text{NdC}_{12}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 36%], 326 $[(\text{NdC}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 40%], 144 $[(\text{Nd})^{3+}$, 66%], 124 $[(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)^+$, 32%], 68 $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8)^+$, 25%], 41 $[(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)^+$, 20%] and 27 $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3)^+$, 41%].

The fragment of the mass spectrum of $[\text{Ce}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$: 595 $[(\text{CeC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_7\text{O}_{10} + 3\text{H})^+$, 62%], 533 $[(\text{CeC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_7 + 3\text{H})^+$, 100%], 409 $[(\text{CeC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{O} + 3\text{H})^+$, 54%], 390 $[(\text{CeC}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4 +$

$2\text{H})^+$, 70%], 363 $[(\text{CeC}_{12}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 42%], 349 $[(\text{CeC}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 51%], 180 $[(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4)^+$, 48%], 140 $[(\text{Ce})^{3+}$, 71%], 68 $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8)^+$, 35%], 41 $[(\text{C}_3\text{H}_5)^+$, 25%] and 27 $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3)^+$, 45%].

The fragment of the mass spectrum of $[\text{Sm}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$: 527 $[(\text{SmC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}_3 + 4\text{H})^+$, 64%], 492 $[(\text{SmC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}_2 + 4\text{H})^+$, 45%], 401 $[(\text{SmC}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 100%], 374 $[(\text{SmC}_{12}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+$, 44%], 180 $[(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4)^+$, 50%], 166 $[(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4)^+$, 45%], 150 $[(\text{Sm})^{3+}$, 61%], 112 $[(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{N}_4)^+$, 70%] and 56 $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)^+$, 42%].

Scheme 2

The fragment of the mass spectrum of $[\text{Eu}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$: 527 $[(\text{EuC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}_3 + 2\text{H})^+, 69\%]$, 491 $[(\text{EuC}_{14}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OCl}_2 + 2\text{H})^+, 58\%]$, 402 $[(\text{EuC}_{14}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+, 100\%]$, 361 $[(\text{EuC}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+, 48\%]$, 334 $[(\text{EuC}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4 + 2\text{H})^+, 55\%]$, 152 $[(\text{Eu})^{3+}, 69\%]$, 124 $[(\text{C}_7\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2)^+, 46\%]$, 97 $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_9\text{N}_2)^+, 62\%]$, 83 $[(\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{N}_2)^+, 37\%]$ and 56 $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_2)^+, \%]$ ²².

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO solution. The spectral data and calculated different bonding parameters for Nd^{3+} and Sm^{3+} complexes are listed in Table 3.

The internal $f-f$ transitions originating with the $4f^n$ configuration of the Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} ions are affected by the influence of the ligands on complexation. The shift of the spectral line to the lower wave number (nephelauxetic effect)²³ with respect to the aqua ion, according to Jorgenson, is due to the decrease in interelectronic repulsion parameters (F_k) in the complexes. The red shift is usually accepted as evidence for a high degree of covalency than existing with aqua compounds²⁴⁻²⁶. The complexes exhibit effective enhancement in the intensity of "hypersensitive" bands from which nephelauxetic effect (β) is calculated by using the following expression,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{v_{\text{complex}}^i}{v_{\text{aquo}}^i}$$

β is the measure of the metal-ligand covalent bonding. The value of β is utilized to estimate the covalency factor ($b^{1/2}$), Sinha parameter i.e. degree of metal-ligand covalency ($\delta\%$) and the covalency angular overlap parameter (η).

Thermal studies :

The thermogravimetric (TG) analyses of the complexes were carried in the temperature range of 30–600 °C in a static nitrogen atmosphere. All the complexes undergo first step decomposition with weight loss 2.97–3.54% (*ca.* 3.02–3.52%), between 180–220 °C due to the loss of the one coordinated water molecule. In the second step, decomposition of the complexes show weight loss 20.22–

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of the ligand.

Fig. 4. Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{La}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$.

Fig. 5. Mass spectrum of the complex $[\text{Nd}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$.

Table 3. Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) and related bonding parameters of lanthanide(III) complexes

Complexes	Band positions	Assignments	Calculated parameters
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	11560	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	$\beta = 0.99362$
	12468	$\rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}, ^4H_{9/2}$	$b^{1/2} = 0.03994$
	13386	$\rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$	$\delta\% = 0.6421$
	13580	$\rightarrow ^4S_{3/2}$	$\eta = 0.00321$
	17182	$\rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}, ^4G_{7/2}$	
	18621	$\rightarrow ^4G_{7/2}$	
	19520	$\rightarrow ^4G_{9/2}$	
$[\text{Nd}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{NO}_3$	11550	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	$\beta = 0.98827$
	12437	$\rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}, ^4H_{9/2}$	$b^{1/2} = 0.05414$
	13297	$\rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$	$\delta\% = 1.18962$
	13560	$\rightarrow ^4S_{3/2}$	$\eta = 0.0059$
	17152	$\rightarrow ^4G_{5/2}, ^4G_{7/2}$	
	18621 } 19128 }	$\rightarrow ^4G_{7/2}$	
$[\text{Sm}(\text{L})\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$	9245	$^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow ^6F_{7/2}$	$\beta = 0.9963$
	10435	$\rightarrow ^6F_{9/2}$	$b^{1/2} = 0.0304$
	18621	$\rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	$\delta\% = 0.37137$
	22421	$\rightarrow ^6P_{5/2}$	$\eta = 0.00185$
	24735	$\rightarrow ^4F_{9/2}$	

31.50% (ca. 20.28–31.47%) in the temperature range 320–380 °C due to the removal of the coordinated and uncoordinated anions. The third step of decomposition is due to the loss of the ligand 41.65–48.49% (ca. 41.61–48.53%) in the temperature range 450–540 °C. The final residues was analyzed by IR spectra and identified as metal oxide corresponds to the calculated value.

Conclusion :

In this article, we describe the synthesis and characterization of a tetradentate macrocyclic ligand and its La^{3+} , Ce^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} and Eu^{3+} complexes. On the basis of absorption spectra we calculate the different parameters i.e. nephelauxetic effect (β), covalency factor ($b^{1/2}$), Sinha parameter ($\delta\%$) and covalency angular over-

lap parameter (η) for Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}. The values of these parameters suggest the metal-ligand covalent bonding. Except La^{III}, all the complexes are paramagnetic in nature. The thermal studies reveal the presence of coordinated water molecule.

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References

1. L. F. Lindoy, "The Chemistry of Macrocyclic Ligand Complexes", Cambridge University Press, UK, 1989.
2. W. J. Evans, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2002, **2**, 642.
3. D. K. Cabiness and D. W. Margerum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6540.
4. M. Shakir, S. Khatoon, S. Parveen and Y. Azim, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2007, **32**, 42.
5. N. Kaltsoyannis and P. Scott, "The *f*-Elements", Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, 1999.
6. H. C. Aspinall, "Chemistry of the *f*-Elements", Taylor & Francis, London, 2001.
7. S. Cotton, "Lanthanide and Actinide Chemistry", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2006.
8. J. Y. Chen and P. R. Selvin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **122**, 657.
9. P. Lebduskova, P. Herman, L. Helm, E. Toth, J. Kofek, K. Binnemans, J. Rudovsky, J. Lukes and A. E. Merbach, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2007, 493.
10. (a) S. Arndt and Okunda, *J. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **102**, 1953; (b) H. Schumann, J. A. Meese-Marktscheffel and L. Esser, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, **95**, 865; (c) W. J. Evans, D. K. Drummond, J. W. Grate, H. M. Zhang and J. L. Alwood, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 3928.
11. W. G. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 110.
12. J. H. Vleck and N. Frank, *Phys. Rev.*, 1929, **34**, 1494.
13. K. Veno and A. E. Martell, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, **60**, 1270.
14. T. Radhakrishna, P. T. Joseph and C. P. Prabhakaran, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 2217.
15. (a) B. M. Gatehouse, S. E. Livingstone and S. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4222; (b) S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 1563.
16. (a) S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 833; (b) S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2005, **61**, 2139; (c) S. Chandra and Sangeetika, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 147.
17. P. J. Lucchesi and W. A. Glasson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 1347.
18. (a) N. F. Curtius and Y. M. Curtius, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **4**, 804; (b) T. Rosu, S. Pasculescu, V. Lazar, C. Chifiriuc and R. Cernat, *Molecule*, 2006, **11**, 904.
19. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
20. J. R. Dyer, "Application of Absorptions Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., Georgia Institute of Technology, 1987.
21. J. H. Beynon, "Mass Spectrometry and its Application to Organic Chemistry", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1960.
22. R. M. Silverstein and F. X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., Wiley, New Delhi, 2007.
23. C. K. Jorgensen, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **4**, 73.
24. S. P. Sinha, *Spectrochim. Acta (A)*, 1966, **22**, 57.
25. C. K. Jorgensen, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1964, **19W**, 424.
26. S. P. Tandon and P. C. Mehta, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1970, **52**, 4313.